

Bromination of 2-Hydroxyfluorene, 2-Hydroxyfluorenone and their Methyl Ether

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2-Hydroxyfluorene and its methyl ether with different quantities of bromine gave the 1-bromo, 1, 7-dibromo and 1, 3, 7-tribromo derivatives. The bromo methyl ethers have been oxidised with sodium dichromate to the corresponding bromofluorenones, some of which have been also obtained through direct bromination of 2-hydroxyfluorenone and its methyl ether. 2-Methoxy-3-bromo-, and 2-methoxy-7-bromofluorene and 2-hydroxy-1, 3-dibromofluorenone have also been synthesised.

Eckert and Langecker¹ brominated *o*-methoxyfluorene and reported the formation of a di- and a tribromo derivative. Their structures were however not established. The present work deals with a systematic study of the bromination of 2-hydroxyfluorene, 2-hydroxyfluorenone and their methyl ethers and it is in continuation of our previous work² on fluorene derivatives.

2-Hydroxyfluorene with one mole of bromine in acetic acid gave a monobromo derivative to which the 1-bromo structure has been assigned for the following reason. Its methyl ether on oxidation gave the corresponding fluorenone derivative. This on heating with cuprous cyanide in dimethyl formamide gave the cyanoderivative which on hydrolysis gave the known 2-methoxy fluorenone-1-carboxylic acid³ as seen by direct comparison. 2-Methoxyfluorene on a similar bromination with one mole of bromine also gave 1-bromo derivative, identical with the methyl ether of 2-hydroxy-1-bromofluorene described above. 2-Hydroxyfluorenone with one mole of bromine gave the 1-bromoderivative. Its methyl ether was found to be identical with the oxidation product of 2-methoxy-1-bromofluorene and with that obtained on bromination of 2-methoxyfluorenone.

2-Methoxyfluorene with two moles of bromine in chloroform gave a dibromo derivative (m. p. 143°) to which the 1, 7-dibromo structure has been assigned as the same product was obtained on further bromination of 2-methoxy-1-bromofluorene and 2-methoxy-7-bromofluorene. The latter has been prepared through the following sequence of reactions: 2-Methoxy-7-nitrofluorene was obtained through the nitration of 2-methoxyfluorene according to Ishikawa and Okazaki³. This was reduced to the amino derivative which was diazotised in the presence of hydrobromic acid. On boiling the diazonium bromide with copper powder the 7-bromo derivative was obtained. This compound has been prepared previously through a different route by Campbell and Hasan⁴. On oxidation with sodium dichromate in glacial acetic acid it gave 2-methoxy-7-bromofluorenone. Similarly 2-methoxy 1, 7-dibromofluorene on oxidation with sodium dichromate gave the corresponding fluorenone derivative. Eckert and Langecker¹ brominated 2-methoxyfluorene in acetic acid and obtained a dibromo derivative (m. p. 121°) to which they did not assign any structure.

2-Hydroxyfluorene with excess (5 moles) of bromine in acetic acid gave a tribromo derivative to which the 1, 3, 7-tribromo structure has been assigned as its methyl ether was identical with the tribromo derivative obtained on further bromination of 2-methoxy-1-bromo-, 2-methoxy-3-bromo- and 2-methoxy-7-bromofluorene. The tribromo derivative of unestablished structure reported by Eckert and Langecker has the same melting point.

2-Methoxy-3-bromofluorene mentioned above was synthesised through the following sequence of reactions: 2-methoxy-3-nitrofluorene, prepared by the nitration of 2-hydroxyfluorene, according to Ray and Hull⁵ was methylated and then diazotised in hydrobromic acid solution. The diazonium bromide on heating with a solution of cuprous bromide in hydrobromic acid gave the desired bromo derivative. On oxidation with sodium dichromate solution it gave 2-methoxy-3-bromofluorenone.

2-Methoxy-1, 3, 7-tribromofluorene on oxidation with sodium dichromate gave 1, 3, 7-tribromofluorenone (m. p. 268°). The methoxy tribromofluorenone reported by Eckert and Langecker¹ has the same melting point.

2-Hydroxyfluorenone on bromination with excess of bromine in acetic acid gave the 1, 3-dibromo derivative. Its methyl ether was identical with the dibromo derivative obtained on bromination of 2-methoxyfluorenone and also the dibromo derivative obtained on further bromination of 2-methoxy-1-bromofluorenone and 2-methoxy-3-bromofluorenone.

Experimental

2-Hydroxy-1-bromofluorene: To 2-hydroxyfluorene (1 g.) in acetic acid (5 ml.) bromine (0.8 g.) in acetic acid (2 ml) was added dropwise with stirring. The product obtained on leaving the reaction mixture overnight crystallised from alcohol in colourless needles (0.9 g.), m. p. 159°. (Found Br, 30.99. C₁₃H₉OBr requires Br, 31.41%).

2-methoxy-1-bromofluorene: The above compound (0.5 g.) was refluxed in acetone solution with dimethyl sulphate (0.5 ml) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (1 g.) for 3 hr. on a steam bath. The product obtained

on removal of the solvent and addition of water crystallised from acetic acid in colourless needles (0.3 g.), m. p. 151°-52°. The same product was obtained when 2-methoxy fluorene (1 g.) in acetic acid (5 ml) was treated with bromine (0.7 g.) in acetic acid (2 ml). (Found : Br, 29.52 C₁₄H₁₁OBr requires Br, 29.13%).

2-Hydroxy-1-bromofluorenone : 2-Hydroxyfluorenone (1 g.) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was treated with bromine (0.7 g.) in acetic acid (5 ml) dropwise and with stirring. The product obtained on leaving the mixture overnight crystallised from toluene in yellow needles (0.8 g.), m. p. 214°. (Found : Br, 28.86. C₁₃H₇O₂Br requires Br, 29.02%).

2-Methoxy-1-bromofluorenone : 2-Methoxy-1-bromofluorene (0.5 g.) in glacial acetic acid (15 ml) was refluxed for 1 hr. with sodium dichromate (1.5 g.). The product obtained on dilution with water crystallised from glacial acetic acid in yellow needles (0.3 g.), m. p. 208°. (Found : Br, 27.65 C₁₄H₉O₂Br requires Br, 27.65%).

The same product was obtained when (i) 2-hydroxy-1-bromofluorenone, was refluxed with dimethyl sulphate in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate for 3 hr. and (ii) 2-methoxyfluorenone (1 g.) in acetic acid (5 ml) was treated with bromine (0.7 g.) in glacial acetic acid (5 ml) and the reaction mixture worked up as before after keeping it overnight.

2-Methoxy-1-cyanofluorenone : The above bromo derivative (1 g.) in dimethyl formamide (20 ml) and cuprous cyanide (1 g.) were heated together under reflux for 2 hr. and then filtered. The product obtained on dilution of the filtrate with water crystallised from toluene in golden yellow needles (0.6 g.), m. p. 294°. (Found : C, 76.54 ; H, 3.55 ; N, 5.46. C₁₅H₉O₂N requires C, 76.60 ; H, 3.82 ; N, 5.68%).

2-Methoxyfluorenone-1-carboxylic acid : The above cyano derivative (1 g.) in alcohol (100 ml) was refluxed with potassium hydroxide (4 g. in 10 ml. water) on a steam bath for 8 hr. The solvent was removed and the reaction mixture was acidified with conc. hydrochloric acid. The acid obtained was further purified by extraction with sodium bicarbonate solution. It crystallised from dilute acetic acid in yellow flakes (0.3 g.), m. p. 241°. Mixed m. p. with the known 2-methoxyfluorenone-1-carboxylic acid² was not depressed.

2-Methoxy-1, 7-dibromofluorene : 2-Methoxyfluorene (1 g.) in chloroform (10 ml) was treated dropwise with bromine (1.5 g.) in chloroform (5 ml) with stirring. The solvent was then removed and the residue obtained was crystallised from acetic acid in colourless needles (0.8 g.), m. p. 143°. (Found : Br, 44.79. C₁₄H₁₀OBr₂ requires Br, 45.16%).

The same compound was obtained on bromination of (i) 2-methoxy-1-bromofluorene (1 g.) in chloroform (10 ml) with bromine (0.7 g.) in chloroform (5 ml) and (ii) 2-methoxy-7-bromofluorene (1 g.) described later with bromine (0.7 g.) in chloroform solution.

2-Methoxy-1, 7-dibromofluorenone : The above dibromo derivative (1 g.) was refluxed in acetic acid (20 ml.) with sodium dichromate (3 g.) for 1 hr. The

product obtained crystallised from glacial acetic acid in orange needles (0.8 g.), m. p. 237°. (Found : Br, 43.22. C₁₄H₈O₂Br requires Br, 43.45%).

2-Methoxy-7-aminofluorene : 2-Methoxy-7-nitrofluorene³ (2 g.) was dissolved in hot alcohol (20 ml.) and to the hot solution sodium hydrosulphite (5 g.) in water (10 ml) was added. The mixture was refluxed on a steam bath for 2 hr. The solvent was then removed and water was added. The product obtained crystallised from alcohol in colourless flakes (1.2 g.), m. p. 203°. Ishikawa and Okazaki³ gave the m. p. 204°.

2-Methoxy-7-bromofluorene : The above amino-fluorene (1.5 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (15 ml) and hydrobromic acid (3 ml.) was added. The solution was cooled to 0° and diazotised with sodium nitrite (0.6 g.) in water (5 ml). It was kept at that temperature for 1 hr. and then heated with copper powder (0.5 g.) to boiling. The solution was filtered hot and the filtrate diluted with water. The separated solid crystallised from petroleum ether in yellow cubes (0.3 g.), m. p. 109°. Campbell and Hasan⁴ gave m. p. 108°-110°.

2-Methoxy-7-bromofluorenone : The above bromo compound (1 g.) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml.) was refluxed with sodium dichromate (3 g.) for 1 hr. The solid obtained on dilution with water crystallised from dilute acetic acid in red needles (0.9 g.), m. p. 147°. (Found : Br, 27.58. C₁₄H₉O₂Br requires Br, 27.65%).

2-Methoxy-3-bromofluorene : 2-Methoxy-3-amino-fluorene⁵ (1.5 g) prepared from 2-methoxy-3-nitrofluorene⁵, was dissolved in acetic acid and hydrobromic acid (3 ml) was added. The solution was cooled to 0° and sodium nitrite (0.8 g.) in water (10 ml) was added dropwise with stirring. The solution was kept at this temperature for 2 hr. and then added slowly to a boiling solution of cuprous bromide (prepared from 3 g. of copper sulphate) in hydrobromic acid (10 ml). After boiling for 10 min. the reaction mixture was filtered hot. The filtrate was diluted with water and the separated product crystallised from dilute acetic acid in yellow needles (0.3 g.), m. p. 185° (Found : Br, 28.98. C₁₄H₁₀OBr requires Br, 29.13%).

2-Methoxy-bromofluorenone : 2-Methoxy-3-bromofluorene (0.5 g.) in glacial acetic acid (20 ml) was refluxed for 1 hr. with sodium dichromate (1.5 g.). The product separating on dilution with water crystallised from acetic acid in orange needles (0.3 g.), m. p. 201°. (Found : Br, 27.64. C₁₄H₉O₂Br requires Br, 27.65%).

2-Hydroxy-1, 3, 7-tribromofluorene : 2-Hydroxyfluorene (1 g.) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was treated with bromine (4 g.) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml.) dropwise and with stirring. The solid which separated crystallised from benzene in colourless needles (1.8 g.), m. p. 190° (Found Br, 57.62 C₁₃H₇OBr₃ requires Br, 57.20%).

2-Methoxy-1, 3, 7-tribromofluorene : The above tribromo derivative (0.5 g.) in acetone (20 ml) was refluxed with dimethyl sulphate (0.5 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (1 g.) for 3 hr. The product obtained crystallised from acetic acid in colourless needles (0.2 g.), m. p. 192-193°. (Found : Br, 55.40. C₁₄H₉OBr₃ requires Br, 55.39%).

The same product was obtained when (i) 2-methoxyfluorene, (ii) 2-methoxy-1-bromofluorene, (iii) 2-methoxy-3-bromofluorene and (iv) 2-methoxy-7-bromofluorene in acetic acid were treated with excess of bromine in acetic acid.

2-Hydroxy-1, 3-dibromofluorene : 2-Hydroxyfluorenone (1 g.) in acetic acid (20 ml.) was treated with bromine in acetic acid (20% ; 20 ml) dropwise and with stirring. The product obtained crystallised from acetic acid in golden yellow needles (1.2 g.), m. p. 237°. (Found : Br, 45.04. $C_{13}H_8O_2Br_2$ requires Br, 45.16%).

2-Methoxy-1, 3-dibromofluorenone : Obtained by refluxing the above dibromo derivative (0.5 g.) in acetone for 4 hr. with dimethyl sulphate (0.5 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (1 g.) crystallised from acetic acid in yellow needles (0.4 g.), m. p. 191°. (Found : Br, 43.00. $C_{14}H_8O_2Br_2$ requires Br, 43.45%).

The same compound was obtained when (i) 2-methoxyfluorenone (1 g.) in acetic acid was brominated with bromine (2 g.) in acetic acid ; (ii) 2-methoxy-1-bromofluorenone (1 g.) was treated with bromine (1 g.) in acetic acid ; and (iii) 2-methoxy-3-bromofluorenone (0.5 g) was treated with bromine (0.5 g.) in acetic acid dropwise with stirring.

2-Methoxy-1, 3, 7-tribromofluorenone : 2-Methoxy-1, 3, 7-tribromofluorene (1 g.) in acetic acid (20 ml.) was refluxed with sodium dichromate (3 g.) for 1 hr. The separated solid crystallised from glacial acetic acid in golden yellow needles (0.8 g.), m. p. 271°. (Found : Br, 53.63. $C_{14}H_7O_2Br_3$ requires Br, 53.67%).

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